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An Investigation into the Economic Advantages of Quality Certification for Manufacturing Companies, Sri Lanka

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ABSTRACT

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO), is a non-governmental and independent organization that aims to promote and establish voluntary standards to improve organizations' quality consciousness for customers. ISO standards are designed to help organizations operate more efficiently and effectively, reduce waste and errors, and enhance customer satisfaction. These standards cover a broad range of areas, such as quality management, environmental management, information security, and social responsibility.

Organizations seek ISO certification to demonstrate their commitment to meeting these standards and to enhance their reputation in the marketplace. By obtaining ISO certification, companies can improve their customer relationship management by showing that they have implemented processes and procedures that are in line with international standards for quality and efficiency.

This study seeks to determine whether ISO certification leads to improvements in firms' efficiency by analyzing their performance before and after certification. The study uses a descriptive research method, which involves collecting data through surveys, interviews, and other methods to gain a deeper understanding of the benefits of ISO certification. The results of the study show that the selected companies have made significant progress in productivity, profitability, and other administrative areas after adopting ISO standards compared to their performance before certification. This improvement can be attributed to the adoption of ISO standards, which have helped the company identify areas for improvement, implement better processes and procedures, and reduce waste and errors.

Overall, ISO certification can be an effective way for organizations to improve their operations and enhance their reputation in the marketplace. By adopting ISO standards, companies can demonstrate their commitment to quality, efficiency, and customer satisfaction, which can ultimately lead to greater success and profitability.

KEYWORDS: ISO, Quality, Manufacturing Firm, Profitability & Administrative Operation

INTRODUCTION

Since its introduction in 1987, the ISO 9000 standard for quality management systems has had a significant impact on the global economy. Many firms seek certification by the ISO 9000 standard, and the standard is now widely adopted globally by companies seeking certification. The adoption of ISO standards is increasing among firms worldwide due to the numerous benefits it offers. ISO implementation represents a transformation from poor management performance to a total quality management approach in the organization. The economic contribution of ISO standards to the economy and companies is significant, as it improves productivity and performance in all sectors. The primary purpose of ISO is to improve quality management, and it deals with the overall management of an organization. The application of ISO standards makes it easier for consumers to choose quality goods and services, thereby promoting consumer satisfaction and loyalty. ISO standards have made the world safer, cleaner, and more efficient, with applications ranging from food safety to computers, healthcare, and new technology. ISO offers positive support for effective utilization of a firm's wealth, thereby enhancing the overall economic growth of the company. As such, ISO certification can be a valuable asset for firms seeking to improve their operations, reputation, and profitability. "Economic benefits" refer to the measurable financial advantages generated by an organization, such as net income, revenue, return on investment, and net cash flow. These benefits can be used to make informed business decisions, policy decisions, and market analyses. Measures such as consumer and producer surplus are often used by policymakers as economic benefit measures.

In light of the above, the present study aims to understand the economic benefits derived from adopting ISO standards in selected manufacturing companies in Lanka Industrial State, Sapugaskanda. By analyzing the economic impact of ISO certification, this study seeks to identify the economic advantages of ISO certification in terms of increased productivity, improved quality control, and enhanced customer satisfaction.

The economic benefits of ISO certification can be significant for organizations. ISO certification can lead to increased profitability, improved operational efficiency, and better risk management, all of which contribute to a company's bottom line. By reducing waste, streamlining processes, and improving quality control, ISO certification can help organizations operate more efficiently and effectively, leading to increased revenue and profits. Moreover, ISO certification can enhance customer confidence and loyalty, which can lead to increased sales and revenue. By demonstrating a commitment to quality and customer satisfaction, ISO-certified organizations can differentiate themselves from their competitors and establish a strong brand reputation in the marketplace.

Overall, the study presents valuable insights into the advantages of adopting ISO standards, which can be used to inform business decisions, policy decisions, and market analyses.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In a study in 2000 by K Subrahmanya Bhat and R Jagadeesh on "ISO 9000 implementation in Indian industries: A study of its reasons and benefits" explore the process and outcomes of ISO certification in Indian industries.

The study examines various criteria, including the benefits of certification and the challenges that organizations face during the certification process. Additionally, the authors provide recommendations for improving the effectiveness of industries, such as implementing quality policies, addressing customer complaints, and utilizing audit feedback to enhance customer satisfaction. By analyzing the experiences and insights of Indian industries that have pursued ISO certification, this study provides valuable guidance for organizations seeking to improve their quality management systems and customer relationships.

In a study in 1984 on "Prices, Product Qualities and Asymmetric Information: The Competitive Case" by Russell Cooper and T. W. Ross investigate the reasons behind firms' decisions to pursue ISO 9000 certification. The study finds that firms seek certification voluntarily, as a means of improving their ability to control quality management processes within the market. This decision is driven by the desire to avoid potential customer dissatisfaction and regulatory non-compliance, which may occur when signals of quality management are inadequate. The authors emphasize that ISO certification helps firms demonstrate their commitment to quality, and to gain a competitive advantage in their respective industries. By exploring the motivations and benefits of ISO certification from the perspective of firms, this study sheds light on the importance of quality management processes for long-term success in the marketplace.

Musbah Maatgi, in a study in 2014 on "An exploratory study to examine relationships between the work environment and success of ISO 9000 implementation in the context of SMEs" focus the study on small manufacturing firms, where the successful implementation of ISO standards and barriers to ISO certification are explored. Through the implementation of ISO standards, firms can create positive changes in their operations, establish a quality culture, and improve their infrastructure. The study identifies key factors that can inhibit the adoption of ISO strategies and suggests ways to reduce these barriers. The ultimate goal is to create an environment in which firms can successfully adopt ISO standards and become more quality conscious. This study is significant because it sheds light on the challenges that small manufacturing firms face when implementing ISO standards, and provides insights into how these challenges can be overcome to achieve positive outcomes for the firms.

In a study titled "Lessons taught by Baldrige winners" (1994), by Niall Brennan examine the financial data of manufacturing firms that have been certified under ISO 9000. They also analyze the costs of implementing ISO 9000 standards to understand the annual costs and benefits to the company. Additionally, they investigate whether receiving the Baldrige Award and ISO 9000 certification is economically attractive for businesses, based on data from Baldrige award winners. The authors conclude that the survey conducted provides useful insights for implementing quality management practices in organizations.

The paper titled "Impact of the ISO 9000 series standards on industrial marketing" by Wade Ferguson (1996) discusses the management standards of ISO 9000 and its significance in building credibility for communicating with the buyers of the company. This study emphasizes the value of institutional

agents as a signal of superior but unobservable attributes which provide benefits to the organization. The authors conclude that their findings will be useful for managers and institutional agents to reduce problems related to management standards.

The paper titled "The longitudinal effects of the ISO 9000 certification process on business performance" by Milé Terziovski, Damien Power and Amrik S Sohal, (2003) explore the impact of ISO implementation on the financial performance of an organization, considering the coherence of technology in its setup. The study highlights the effectiveness of ISO in reducing costs and improving operational efficiency through the production of defect-free products and standardized procedures. The paper emphasizes the importance of waste reduction in improving the overall financial performance of an organization. The authors conclude that their study provides insights into process management and strategy, which can help organizations to improve their performance.

In an empirical study by Olufemi I. Falope and Olubanjo T. Ajilore on the "Working capital management and corporate profitability: evidence from panel data analysis of selected quoted companies in Nigeria" discuss the impact of implementing and certifying companies according to ISO 9000 standards. The benefits of implementing ISO 9000 standards have a positive effect on the profitability of the business, and the economic outcomes of certified and non-certified companies in the study region were analyzed.

The paper titled "Alternative quality improvement practices and organizational performance" by E. E. Adam in 2007 examines the quality management systems standards of Indian manufacturing firms, including critical factors and indicators of organizational performance. The study analyses the relationship between the firm's attributes and critical factors, as well as the relationship between the firm's attributes and the indicators of organizational performance.

In a study titled "An international study of quality improvement approach and firm performance" by Everett E. Adam, Lawrence M. Corbett, Benito E. Flores and Norma Harrison (2014) compare the workmanship performance of ISO certified and non-certified organizations in the construction industry. They conduct a case study of a specific organization that has implemented ISO 9001 and compare its performance to that of an organization that has not. The study provides insights into the workmanship performance of both certified and non-certified organizations under ISO standards.

M. Casadesus and S. Karapetrovic in a study in 2005 on "An empirical study of the benefits and costs of ISO 9001:2000 compared to ISO 9001:1994" evaluate the effectiveness of the industry that is certified under ISO 9001, and to identify the quality and performance of the organization. The study provides useful insights for all types of organizations to develop a strategic management system for their ISO-certified operations.

R. H. Hayes and Pisano, G. P (1994), paper titled "Beyond world class: the new manufacturing strategy" argue that to remain competitive in today's global economy, companies must adopt a new approach to manufacturing that focuses on continuous improvement, flexibility, and innovation. Overall, the book provides a roadmap for companies looking to adopt a more

advanced and effective manufacturing strategy that can help them stay ahead of the competition and thrive in today's fast-paced business environment.

S. Liebesman, J. Mroz, (2001), study on "ISO 9000 : 2000 product support initiative - effort to provide value to users grows out of standards validation work" discuss the goal of the initiative that help organizations better understand and implement the ISO 9000 standards, particularly in the area of product support. This includes providing guidance on how to incorporate product support requirements into the ISO 9000 quality management system, as well as how to measure and improve product support performance. It is also says that the initiative is based on the recognition that product support is a critical component of overall customer satisfaction and that organizations that excel in this area are more likely to be successful in the marketplace. Overall, it says that the ISO 9000:2000 product support initiative represents a commitment to continuous improvement and a recognition of the importance of product support in ensuring customer satisfaction and business success.

D. Prajogo (2009), study on "Experiences of Australian firms in implementing ISO 9001: a comparison of the 1994 and 2000 versions". The paper discusses the key changes that were made to the ISO 9001 standard in 2000, including the introduction of the process approach and the emphasis on continual improvement. It also examines the challenges that Australian firms faced in implementing the standard and the strategies they used to overcome these challenges. The research found that while the 2000 version of ISO 9001 was more complex and challenging to implement than the 1994 version, it also provided greater benefits to organizations that were able to successfully implement it. These benefits included improved customer satisfaction, increased employee engagement, and greater operational efficiency.

N. M. Vaxevanidis, Z. Krivokapic, S. Stefanatos, P. Dasic and G. Petropoulos in 2006 the study titled "An Overview and a comparison of ISO 9000:2000 Quality System Standards with related automotive (QS9000, ISO/TS 16949) and TQM models (MBNQA AND EFQM)" discuss the evolution of the ISO 9000 standards and the changes made in the 2000 version of the standard. It then compares ISO 9000:2000 with other quality system standards, such as QS9000 and ISO/TS 16949, which are specific to the automotive industry. The paper examines the similarities and differences between these standards, including their requirements and focus areas. The paper also discusses two Total Quality Management (TQM) models, the Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award (MBNQA) and the European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM) model. It compares these models with ISO 9000:2000 and the automotive quality system standards, examining their similarities and differences and the benefits of implementing these models. Overall, the paper provides a comprehensive overview and comparison of various quality system standards and TQM models, highlighting the similarities and differences between them and their potential benefits for organizations in different industries. It underscores the importance of understanding the requirements and focus areas of these standards and models to ensure effective implementation and continuous improvement of quality management systems.

D. Y. Patil in 2011 in a study titled "Conscious effect on maintaining the quality in the food processing industry" refers to the intentional effort made by organizations in the food processing industry to maintain and improve the quality of their products and processes. The article discusses the importance of quality in the food processing industry, where even small lapses in quality can have serious consequences for public health and safety. The article emphasizes that maintaining quality requires a conscious effort, from the selection of raw materials to the final product delivery. This involves establishing and following strict quality control measures, as well as implementing continuous improvement initiatives to identify and address any quality issues that arise. The article also highlights the importance of employee training and engagement in maintaining quality. It suggests that organizations should provide regular training and education for their employees on quality control measures and procedures, as well as encourage employees to take an active role in identifying and addressing quality issues. Overall, the article emphasizes the importance of maintaining high-quality standards in the food processing industry and the need for a conscious effort from all stakeholders to ensure product safety and customer satisfaction.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To examine the influence of ISO standards on the economic performance of companies, particularly in terms of their profitability, costs, and revenue management.
- 2) To investigate the impact of ISO standards on the productivity levels of the firm which will focus on identifying the changes in the productivity levels of the firm after the adoption of ISO standards examining the different factors that can influence productivity levels, such as the firm's size, industry, and location, and how the adoption of ISO standards affects these factors.
- 3) To examine the impact of ISO standards on the administrative operations of a firm which will aim to identify the changes in the administrative processes of the organization after implementing ISO standards.

METHODOLOGY

The study is conducted on a group of selected firms located in Lanka Industrial Estate, Sapugaskanda, which is experiencing industrial growth. A significant number of these firms have obtained ISO certification, which makes them suitable for the study.

The descriptive research method is used in this study to gain a deeper understanding of the change in productivity levels of firms upon adopting ISO standards. This method involves collecting and analyzing data through observation, surveys, and secondary sources. The study will analyze previous data to observe the change in productivity levels after the implementation of ISO standards in the selected firms Lanka Industrial Estate, Sapugaskanda, Sri Lanka. The goal of the study is to identify the impact of ISO standards on the productivity levels of the firms and how it has affected their operations. The findings of this study could be useful for firms that are considering implementing ISO standards and wish to understand the potential impact on their productivity levels.

As the focus of this study is to examine the impact of ISO standards on productivity, the research methodology utilized is based on a comparative analysis of productivity before and after the adoption of ISO standards. To achieve this goal, the study employs the descriptive research method and relies primarily on previous reports as a primary source of information. These reports provide valuable data for comparing the productivity component before and after the implementation of ISO standards. As a result, secondary sources of information, such as company records, official reports, and academic articles, are utilized to supplement the data gathered from primary sources. This approach enables a comprehensive analysis of the changes in productivity following the implementation of ISO standards, providing valuable insights for future research in this area.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

- 1) To determine the effect of ISO implementation on a company's profitability, including whether it leads to an increase or decrease in profit."
- 2) The sales of the product may either increase or decrease after the implementation of ISO.
- 3) Productivity is either increased or decreased.
- 4) Has the improvement in dealers and external suppliers resulted in increased sales?
- 5) Assessment of technological differences pre and post certification

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

About ISO

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is a non-governmental, independent organization with members from 162 national bodies. ISO and its members collaborate with experts from around the world to address global challenges and improve standards. ISO aims to promote innovation in terms of products and services, systems, quality, and efficiency. Through its standards, ISO facilitates international trade in various industries, ranging from safety to technology. The impact of ISO's work can be felt everywhere and by everyone. Its standards are widely adopted and respected, and they help ensure consistent quality and safety across different industries and regions. Overall, ISO plays a crucial role in fostering global cooperation and driving progress towards a more sustainable and equitable world.

Economic Benefits of the ISO

ISO has been working towards creating a family of standards for the last 50 years to ensure the quality and safety of products and services provided by ISO-certified companies, which are used by consumers worldwide. This family of standards includes a range of specifications for various areas such as quality management, environmental management, and occupational health and safety.

ISO standards provide customers with the assurance that the management system of the company has been approved by a globally recognized organization. It also helps companies to improve their overall management system and performance, increase customer satisfaction, and reduce costs through the efficient use of resources. The ISO standards have become increasingly important in international trade as they facilitate communication between companies from different countries

and cultures by providing a common language and framework for business processes. It has become an essential tool for

companies to ensure their products and services meet the requirements of customers and regulations.

ANALYSIS AND COMPREHENSION

To analyze the profitability of the firm pre- and post-certification.

Table 1: Table 1: Comparison of Profitability before and after Certification

Before ISO 9000 Certification		After ISO 9000 Certification	
Year	Profitability	Year	Profitability
2017	7.12%	2020	8.86%
2018	7.19%	2021	9.65%
2019	7.22%	2022	9.77%

[Source: company records]

Table 1

The table presented above depicts the analysis of the profitability of the manufacturing industry, which has been statistically assessed before and after the certification of ISO. The study focuses on ISO Certified firms, and their profitability has been analyzed to gain insights into the impact of ISO on the manufacturing firms. The results indicate that ISO standards

have a significant positive impact on the profitability of the firms. According to the firms, the implementation of ISO standards has improved the quality of their products and services, leading to an increase in profitability compared to the previous years. This highlights the effectiveness of ISO standards in improving the overall performance of the manufacturing industry.

COMPARING THE REVENUE PERFORMANCE OF THE FIRM BEFORE AND AFTER CERTIFICATION

Table 2 illustrates the revenue performance of the firm before and after certification

Particulars	Before ISO 9000 Certification		After ISO 9000 Certification	
	Product1	Product 2	Product 1	Product 2
Price	90	85	98	92
Quantity Sold	30	45	47	62
Mark-Up	30	20	30	25
Shipping Charges	35	35	35	35
Profit	51	42.5	53	47.6
Net Income	920	1887.5	1693	2055.2
Total Revenue	1340	2400	2357	2718.2

[Source: company records]

Table 2

The above table provides a comparison of the revenue generated by a firm before and after the certification of ISO 9000. The firm produces two products, Product 1 and Product 2, and the table includes details of the production process, from the consumption of raw materials to the sale of the final product in the market. The revenue generated by each product is calculated based on its sales in the market, taking into account the quantity of product manufactured.

On analyzing the table, it can be observed that the performance of the products after the ISO 9000 certification is good, as compared to the performance before the certification. ISO 9000 certification has a quality-conscious approach towards the installation process of the standard in the firm. This standard ensures that the production process is carried out in a controlled and consistent manner, which results in better quality products and improved revenue for the firm.

TO GAIN AN UNDERSTANDING OF THE CHANGES IN PRODUCTIVITY LEVELS FOLLOWING THE ADOPTION OF ISO CERTIFICATION.

The productivity of firms plays a crucial role in determining the economic growth of a nation. In this category, the study focuses on analyzing the productivity of firms after the certification of ISO 9000. Productivity can be defined as a measure of the efficiency of production, which encompasses various factors such as quality, quantity, and timeliness of production. The productivity of firms can be measured in terms of the output produced with respect to the amount of input utilized in the production process. It is important to note that the productivity of firms has a direct impact on their profitability, where increased productivity results in increased profits. Hence, the study analyzes the impact of ISO 9000 certification on the productivity of firms to understand the role of ISO 9000 in improving the overall efficiency of firms.

Table 3 presents the productivity level of the firm after the adoption of ISO certification.

ISO Certification	Improvement in Manufacturing Techniques	Customers Satisfaction	Technology	Aiding of Employees
ISO 9000 Certified	<i>The business plan was reviewed, analyzed, and updated with new development ideas to improve production quality and reduce wastage.</i>	<p><u>Internal</u> <i>The company experiences an increase in orders from its current customer base and attracts new customers as well. Both the number of orders from existing customers and the number of new customers increase. The firm gains new customers while also seeing an uptick in orders from its existing customer pool.</i></p> <p><u>External</u> <i>The number of external customers using the product or service increases as a result of the improved quality of the product after adopting ISO standards.</i></p>	<i>The firm has discovered new production processes with the aid of research and development (R&D) efforts, thereby enhancing its technological capabilities.</i>	<i>ISO 9000 Standards adoption has resulted in the extension of training to employees in the firm, leading to an improvement in quality service delivery.</i>

[Source: company records]

Table 3

TO UNDERSTAND THE IMPACT OF ADMINISTRATIVE OPERATION CHANGES ON A FIRM'S PERFORMANCE.

Table 4 Demonstrates the Impact of ISO Certification on Administrative Operations

ISO Certification	Internal Audit	Human Resources
ISO 9000 Certified	<i>The adoption of ISO standards encourages firms to review their business processes to assess their effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. This enables firms to establish effective control over their processes and develop them according to their business plans.</i>	<i>A department dedicated to HR is established to analyze TQM (Total Quality Management) and the development of the firm. The department focuses primarily on the welfare of the employees and the society.</i>

[Source: company records]

Table 4

CONCLUSIONS

In the current business environment, it is challenging for companies to sustain and thrive. ISO plays a significant role in guiding companies to improve and meet standards that enable them to compete and succeed. Adopting ISO leads to a systematic approach to work and the adoption of standard practices that reflect as quality goods and services. The study presented above focuses on the changes in various aspects of the organization, including qualitative, productive, and profitability aspects, which translate into various economic benefits for the organization. The analysis of the study provides insights into the positive impacts of adopting ISO standards, and how it can contribute to the growth and development of organizations.

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